

Possible Anti-Ulcer Compounds : Synthesis of New Substituted 10-Acylamino Phenothiazines

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Since phenothiazine group of drugs exhibit certain desired effects required by an ideal anti-ulcer antisecretory drug, a new series of compounds have been synthesised in search of some specific antiulcer agent. The preliminary pharmacological investigations of the hydrochloride salts of the title compounds showed promising results.

MOST of the antiulcer drugs in therapy today lack in their specificity of action. Attempts, therefore, continue to explore for new anti-ulcer drugs devoid of usual peripheral involvement^{1,2}. Phenothiazines have been reported to possess anticholinergic, antispasmodic and local anaesthetic activity^{3,4}, which are the essential requirements of antiulcer drugs. Chlorpormazine in high doses (20 mg/kg) has been reported to possess antigastric secretory and anti-ulcer activity^{5,6}. However, at such high doses, other actions do predominate and hence the reported anti-ulcer activity cannot be specific. Secergan, a new quaternary acylamino-phenothiazine derivative, has been reported to be an effective anti-ulcer and anti-spasmodic drug^{7,8}. But the quaternary compounds are less preferred in comparison to the tertiary analogues because of their unpredictable actions⁹. Introduction of a tertiary amine function in the side chain indeed in some cases, have yielded compounds with selective parasympathetic blockade¹⁰. Hence on theoretical grounds acylaminophenothiazines with tertiary amino group in their side chain shall be more preferable to the quaternary compounds like secergan. Considering the above facts it was thought worthwhile to synthesise 10-acylamino phenothiazines in quest for finding some specific and better anti-ulcer compounds.

A new series of compounds referred to in Chart I were prepared using the procedure¹¹⁻¹⁶ reported for the synthesis of related phenothiazines. Thus appropriately substituted phenothiazines when treated with halo acyl chlorides afforded the corresponding N-haloacyl derivatives. The latter when condensed with tert. butylamine or N-methyl piperazine or N-β-Hydroxyethylpiperazine gave the respective 10-acyl amino phenothiazines (A-I).

Thus 2-methoxy-10-(tert. butylamino)-acetyl (A), 2-methoxy-10-β-(tert. butyl amino)-propionyl (B), 2-methoxy-10-α-(tert. butyl amino)-propionyl (C),

Chart I.

Compd. No.	X	R	Z
A	OCH ₃	CH ₂	NHC(CH ₃) ₃
B	OCH ₃	CH(CH ₃)	NHC(CH ₃) ₃
C	OCH ₃	CH ₂ CH ₂	NHC(CH ₃) ₃
D	Cl	CH ₂	
E	OCH ₃	CH ₂	
F	OCH ₃	CH ₂ CH ₂	
G	OCH ₃	CH(CH ₃)	
H	OCH ₃	CH ₂ CH ₂	
I	OCH ₃	CH(CH ₃)	

A-C as monohydrochlorides and D-I as dihydrochlorides.

2-chloro-10-(4'-methyl-piperazinyl-1')-acetyl (D), 2-methoxy-10-(4'-methylpiperazinyl-1')-acetyl (E), 2-methoxy-10- β -(4'-methyl piperazinyl-1')-propionyl (F), 2-methoxy-10- α -(4'-methyl piperazinyl-1)-propionyl (G), 2-methoxy-10- β -(4'-(β' -hydroxy ethyl)-piperazinyl-1') propionyl (H); and 2-methoxy-10- α -(4'-(β' -hydroxy ethyl)-piperazinyl-1')-propionyl (I) phenothiazines have been prepared.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected and were taken in open capillary tubes. The UV spectral data were recorded using model H 700-308 Hilger spectrophotometer.

Preparation of haloacyl chlorides: Chloroacetyl chloride, α -Bromopropionyl chloride and β -chloropropionyl chloride were synthesized by the procedure reported earlier¹¹⁻¹³

N-(Haloacyl)-phenothiazines: To a solution of the respective phenothiazine (0.1M) in dry benzene, a solution of the appropriate haloacyl chloride (0.15M) in dry benzene (50 ml) was added with stirring at room temperature. The mixture was then refluxed over a steam bath for 4 hr and cooled. After removal of benzene under reduced pressure, the gummy residue was chilled in ice and then triturated with a small quantity of petroleum ether (60°-80°). The product thus separated was filtered and then crystallised with ethanol or propanol to yield the respective N-(Haloacyl)-phenothiazine. Almost all the compounds were obtained in 70% yield.

N-Aminoacyl phenothiazines: A solution of the appropriately substituted N-haloacyl phenothiazine (0.01M) in 15 ml of dry benzene was treated with tert. butylamine or N-methylpiperazine or N- β -hydroxyethylpiperazine (0.025M) as the case may be and the mixture was stirred for half an hour at room temperature, then refluxed under anhydrous conditions over a steam bath for 5 hr. After cooling the mixture was filtered to remove the hydrochloride salt of the unreacted amine. The benzene layer thus obtained was separated and washed well with water to remove the traces of the unreacted amine. This was then treated with 0.1N-HCl solution so that the desired compound forms hydrochloride which remains in the aqueous layer. The aqueous layer was separated, cooled and ammonia solution was added to it dropwise until complete precipitation (pH 8.5 approx.). This was extracted with ether or chloroform and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate overnight. The solution was filtered and the solvent removed from the filtrate under reduced pressure. The remaining solid was then taken up in dry ether and dry hydrochloric acid gas passed to obtain the respective hydrochlorides of 10-N-(acylamino) phenothiazines. The purity of the crystallised sample was checked over tlc.

Various compounds thus prepared are listed in Chart 1 and their chemical and analytical data appear in the Table 1.

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TABLE 1—N-ACYLAMINO PHENOTHIAZINE HYDROCHLORIDES

Product	Recrystallisation solvent	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	% Analysis						Absorption spectra in H ₂ O	
					C		H		N		λ_{max} mn	ϵ_{max}
					Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found		
A.	1 : 2-Dichloroethane	217 Dec.	69	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ N ₂ SO ₂ Cl	60.23	59.98	6.11	6.09	7.30	6.98	237	10500
											250	09275
											265	09050
B.	Benzene : Petroleum ether	180	75	C ₂₀ H ₂₅ N ₂ SO ₂ Cl	61.14	61.30	6.14	6.14	7.13	6.39	256	08950
											259	09475
C.	Butylacetate : Petroleum ether	200	77	C ₂₀ H ₂₅ N ₂ SO ₂ Cl	61.14	61.24	6.14	6.30	7.13	7.25	234	10824
											255	10850
D.	Ethanol : Petroleum ether (1 : 1)	237 Dec.	79	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ N ₃ SO Cl ₃	51.07	50.86	4.96	4.88	9.40	8.74	236	13500
											260	09900
E.	Ethanol : Cyclohexane (1 : 1)	216 Dec.	68	C ₂₀ H ₂₅ N ₃ SO ₂ Cl ₂	54.23	53.96	5.69	5.49	9.49	8.63	238	17165
											265	11267
F.	Propan-2-01	217	71	C ₂₁ H ₂₇ N ₃ SO ₂ Cl ₂	55.27	55.38	5.96	5.76	9.20	9.31	233	13872
											260	10636
G.	Propan-2-01	188	71	C ₂₁ H ₂₇ N ₃ SO ₂ Cl ₂	55.27	55.42	5.96	5.80	9.20	9.35	232	15953
											257	10034
H.	Propan-1-01	193	79	C ₂₂ H ₂₉ N ₃ SO ₃ Cl ₂	54.32	54.45	6.01	6.30	8.64	8.78	235	15244
											247	11951
											260	11951
I.	Chloroform	172 Dec.	86	C ₂₂ H ₂₉ N ₃ SO ₃ Cl ₂	54.32	54.45	6.01	6.24	8.64	8.82	236	12561
											260	09915

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References

1. P. BASS, R. A. PURDON, M. A. PATTERSON and D. E. BUTLER, *J. Pharmac. Exp. Therap.*, 1966, **152**, 104.
2. J. L. THOMPSON, "Medicinal Research Series", Vol. 6, Marcel Dekker Inc., New York, 1972, p. 155.
3. V. N. SHARMA, N. S. PANCHOLI, H. L. SHARMA, R. L. MITAL and DHARMA CHANDRA, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1971, **60**, 1262.
4. V. N. SHARMA, R. L. MITAL, S. P. BANERJEE and H. L. SHARMA, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1971, **14**, 68.
5. R. N. TIEDE, C. J. PFEIFFER and G. H. GASS, *Nature*, 1963, **199**, 1296.
6. A. G. RADMAN and G. B. WEST, *Brit. J. Pharmac.*, 1971, **41**, 167.
7. J. TOMENIUS, *Acta Med. Scand.*, 1957, **157**, 11.
8. M. GORDON, "Psychopharmacological Agents", Vol. II, Academic Press, New York, 1969, p. 135.
9. S. V. ANICHKOV and I. S. ZAVODAKAYA, "The Experimental Basis of Gastric Ulcer Pharmacotherapy", Pergamon Press, Oxford 1968.
10. H. G. PARDO, R. VARGAS, J. CATO and J. LAGUNA, *J. Pharmac. Exp. Therap.*, 1956, **116**, 377.
11. R. ADAMS and L. H. ULICH, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, **42**, 599.
12. P. E. FRANLAND and W. E. GARMER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, **105**, 1100.
13. C. PUAL and C. MILLER-LOBECK, *Ber.*, 1931, **64**, 2142.
14. S. V. ZHRUSULEV and A. N. GRITSENKO, *Zhur. Obschi. Khim.*, 1957, **26**, 3385; *Chem. Abs.*, 1957, **51**, 9623.
15. L. TOLDY, I. TOTI, M. FUKETE and J. BORSY, *Acta Chim. Hung.*, 1965, **44**, 301.
16. H. L. SHARMA, S. P. BANERJEE, V. N. SHARMA and R. L. MITAL, *Ann. Soc. Sci. Bruxelles*, 1970, **84**, 55.